

Football Betting and Depression among Youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State

Mina Margaret Ogbanga (PhD)

River State University

mina.ogbanga@ust.edu.ng

Idongesit Gladys Hilary

*Department of Sociology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni Port
Harcourt*

Abstract

The study investigated football betting and depression among youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The study was guided with one research question, one objective as well as one hypothesis. The scope of the study was delimited into geographical scope and the content scope which addressing the issue football betting and depression. They were synthesized to explain the nexus between football betting and depression. Methodologically, the study adopted a correlation research design using quantitative research approach to get the view of the sample respondents. The sample size of 400 was used to determine through census sampling technique. The research instrument was questionnaire. The validity of the instrument was content validity, while the reliability was obtained through test-retest technique which gave an index of 0.80. The method of data analysis included the chart, mean and T-test. The findings of the study revealed the reasons for football betting among football betting youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State and also found that various depressed symptoms characterized the football betting games such as financial constraints, conflict with family members, emotional traumas and many more. It was recommended among others the need for youths to consider reaching out to mental health professionals, such as a therapist or counselor, or social workers who can provide personalized support and guidance as this can help them to understand and address the underlying causes of their depressive symptoms related to football betting.

Introduction

Football (soccer) is one of the most popular sports in the world which is associated with important betting activities (Armstrong & Carroll, 2017). A common belief, widely spread among those who participate in football betting activities, is that knowledge and expertise on football lead to better prediction skills for match outcomes (Armstrong & Carroll, 2017). This belief precipitated the high increase in the number of youths who participate in football betting. Football betting is the activity of predicting football results and placing a wager on the outcome. The frequency of football bet varies from culture to culture. Uzochukwu and Ohiri (2021) maintained that in recent times, the economic hardship in Nigeria is becoming unbearable hence, most people are finding it difficult to meet their basic needs. They further stated that unemployment and underemployment rate is on the increase, and businesses are collapsing and depression rate is increasing daily which all result to people involving in different risky behaviour to survive. One of the risky behaviour is gambling which has been reported to be related to some criminal behaviour and prominent amongst them is football betting which most Nigerian youths are addicted to. (Oyebisi, et al., 2012). The Nigerian sports betting (online and offline) and gaming industry has grown geometrically in the past few years (Uzochukwu & Ohiri, 2021). Accordingly, to them, this remarkable growth can be attributed to the country's population and increased access to the internet via enabled internet devices such as mobile phones, tablets, laptop, desktops etc. Many adolescents, youths, young adult, educated and non-educated Nigerians are involved in football betting (Eboh, 2015). Football betting has become part of mainstream culture through the entertainment, leisure, sport, and tourism industries and it is a significant source of revenue to governments and private enterprises

(Eboh et al., 2012). It also comes in different forms ranging from betting and prediction, lottery, casino betting and virtual games. Football betting also poses a source of harm and concern to some Nigerians due to its negative impact on individuals, families and communities through problem gambling (Deans et al., 2017). While most people handle recreational football betting in a controlled way, many get addicted. It is therefore essential that football betting and problem gambling are well understood, and that the regulation of football betting at individual, community, industry and government levels is well informed.

Statistically, about 60 million Nigerians between the ages of 18 and 40 are involved in active sports betting. On average, these punters spend roughly ₦3,000 Naira every day on bets enterprise (Eboh et al., 2012). For instance, data report from Klynveld and Goerdeler (2016) revealed that a leading sports betting company in Nigeria makes an average monthly turnover of \$10 million dollars. Sport betting shops can now be spotted in almost every street in Lagos and new ones are popping up daily. In Nigeria gambling is regulated by the National Lottery Regulatory Commission (NLRC) and it is worthy to note that all forms of gambling including football betting are restricted from all residents of Nigeria below 18 years enterprise (Eboh et al., 2012). The present paper is on the trends of football betting and the change in the appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the nexus between football betting and depression among football betting youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. In specific terms, the objective is to;

1. To investigate how the trends of football betting affect change in the appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Hypothesis

Ho₁ The more the youths involves themselves in football betting and also becomes unsuccessful in the game, the more they become depress in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

Significance of the Study

This study would be useful as it will reveal the relationship between football betting and depression among football betting youths in Nigeria. The study will be of a huge benefit to government, parents, teachers, counsellors, social workers and future researchers. The study would be beneficial to government in the sense that the study will reveal the prevalence of pathological betting and its negative effects on the mental health of the youths. This will enable government to initiate laws that will regulate football betting and other gambling activities. The government through this study will be informed of the importance of social workers in addressing some of these social issues.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms are operationally defined;

Depression: This is a mental disorder characterized by persistent sadness and loss of interest in activities one usually enjoys.

Betting: Betting is the action of gambling money, possessions, time, or something else on the outcome of something, such as a game or race. In other words, the act or practice of playing games of chance for a stake; usually money. We can also, in most cases, use the word ‘**gambling**’ with the same meaning.

Football betting: This refers to the activity of predicting football results and placing a wager on the outcome.

Football Betting Youths: These are young people between the ages of 18-40 who engage in football betting in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Trends of Football Betting in Nigeria

Motorcycle Racing: With the rest of the events, the situation is similar. Motorcycle racing allows us to bet on the winner of the test or make a combine. They are motorcycle races on a speedway-type circuit where you only turn to the left side. Each participant has their quotas, and the race lasts only 1 minute.

Virtual Motorcycle Racing: In these speed cycling races, you can bet on the winner from a group of 8 runners or make a combine. As in other virtual sports, the race is short but exciting.

Greyhound Racing: Greyhound racing is practically identical to motorcycle racing. In them, the virtual dogs must go around a circular circuit, and before it, we can bet on the winner or make a combined. The dog with the lowest odds does not have to win here, as it does in real life.

Horse and Trotter Racing: You can also bet on horse races. As with the other specialties, you bet only on the winner or in combinations. You will see a race in a virtual racetrack with a quite successful setting. Trotting competitions are a bit slower and maybe a bit more boring.

Match Bet: This is the simplest form of football betting in which you pick the result of a football match. You can bet on the three different outcomes which are a home team to win, the away team to win or a draw. It's important to note that match bets are paid out on the outcome after 90 minutes, so if the scores are level then, the draw is the winning bet, irrespective of the outcome after extra time or penalties.

Bet Builder/Same Game Multi: Bet builders are one of the newer additions to football betting and have become one of the more popular ways to bet on the sport in recent years. Sometimes referred to as same game multis, these bets are effectively an accumulator of outcomes from a single match rather than a number of matches. These bets are obviously less likely to come in because of the number of outcomes that need to happen. However, they are perfect if you are knowledgeable about both teams and want to place small-stake bets at the bigger odds that can be

realised by combining numerous outcomes, such as the number of yellow cards, corners and goal scorers, rather than betting on each individual market. You can also include player props, which we explain below, in bet builders. Player props are also becoming a popular form of betting on their own.

Player Props/Player Stats: This is a way of showing how the football betting market has continued to evolve with an in-depth set of markets released for various Premier League and international matches. This is different to the goal scoring or card markets, and includes the ability to bet on players to have a certain number of shots, tackles and even off sides. There are also ever-growing prop markets that lead to some intriguing bets such as how many free-kicks, goal-kicks and throw-ins there are in a match. What's on offer differs widely from bookmaker to bookmaker, but one of the bookies with the most player props available is [bet365](#). There is also now the option to bet on the number of passes a player makes in a match, which can be a fascinating bet to follow and allows customers to use their own research before making the specific bet (Hing, Lamont, Vitartas & Fink 2015)..

Whole-goal handicap: *Liverpool -1, Arsenal +2*. The figures next to each team are applied to their score in the match. If you bet on Liverpool, you win if they win by a two-goal margin or more. You lose if they draw or lose. And you get your stake back if they win by a one-goal margin, which is cancelled out by the -1, making the handicap result a draw. If you bet on Arsenal, you win if they win, if they draw or if they lose by only a one-goal margin. You lose if they lose by a

three-goal margin or more. And you get your stake back if they lose by a two-goal margin, which is cancelled out by the +2, making the

European handicap bet: A European handicap is similar to an Asian handicap but with two main differences: one is that the draw remains an option and the other is that the handicaps are only ever whole numbers.

Half-time/full-time: You can bet on the result of the first half and/or the second half. You can bet on the home team, away team or draw for one or both halves. This bet is for the more advanced football fan who has prior knowledge to indicate the teams who start or finish matches strongly or weakly. Knowing the starting line-ups and whether key players are missing through injury or being rested can also be an advantage with this type of bet.

Double Chance: You can bet on two of the three outcomes of the match to increase your chance of winning. The combinations are:

- Home team or draw
- Away team or draw
- Home team or away team

If either of your combinations wins you will be paid out. The odds are lower than betting on just a single match outcome as there is more chance of winning, but this bet is good for bettors who want to reduce the element of risk.

Goal scorer Betting: As it suggests, this is a bet on a particular player to score during a match. You can bet on various outcomes, such as your selection to be the first or last goalscorer in the match or to score at any time during it. The odds on them scoring at any time will be shorter because there is obviously a greater chance of that happening. These bets are often quite good to take a chance on when a player has been in a rich vein of form, or if a team is overall better than their opponents making a player more likely to find the back of the net. You can choose from any of the players on the pitch, with bookmakers often having good offers to go with some of the markets within goal scoring and boosts throughout the different matches, depending on how they're going.

Correct Score/Scorecast/Wincast: A correct score bet is one in which you predict the final score of a match. Remember that this will be the outcome after 90 minutes in cup ties that could go to extra time and/or penalties. The prices for correct score bets are often attractive but, of course, predicting the exact score is far from easy. A Scorecast is a bet that combines selecting a goalscorer and the correct score. For example, you can bet on Mohamed Salah to score and Liverpool to win 2-0. Again, the odds on such bets have higher odds because you are betting on the likelihood of two outcomes. Some bookmakers will also let you choose the goalscorer in a Scorecast to be the first, last or at any time. A Wincast is similar to a Scorecast, but involves selecting a goalscorer and the outcome of the match rather than the correct score. The odds will not be as high as a Scorecast because it is easier to predict the outcome rather than the scoreline.

Over and Under Betting: This is a bet on the total number of times an event (for example, goals, corners, yellow cards) will happen during a match. Bookmakers allocate a baseline number to a

match and you can bet on whether there will be more (over) or fewer (under) than that number. The baseline number will never be a whole number, which guarantees that the outcome will be one of two: over or under. (You can't score half a goal.) So in a match where a bookmaker is offering Over or Under 2.5 goals, you win if you bet on Over and three or more goals are scored, but you lose if the total is none, one or two. Likewise, if you bet on Under, you win if none, one or two goals are scored and lose if the total is three or higher.

Draw No Bet: This is where you bet on the outcome of a match, but if it ends in a draw then you will get your stake back. However, this means the odds will usually be lower than other markets.

In-play betting: As the name suggests, in-play betting involves making a bet on an outcome during an event, such as backing the next team to score in a match you are watching on television. Bookmakers offer several markets, such as the next goalscorer, which team will win the next corner or throw-in, or who will be the next player to be shown a yellow card. There are also some great markets to follow on in-play sites such as 'corner races' and on bet365 certain specials within the prop markets available such as shots and player shots.

Research Methodology

Research Design

Correlation research design was adopted in this study. The correlation research design refers to a relationship between two variables that have nothing to do with any extraneous variable. It is a

non-experimental research method where the researcher has to assess the statistical relationship between the two variables to reach the desired outcome (Wilson, 2020).

Area of Study

Obio-Akpor is a local government area in the metropolis of Port Harcourt, one of the major centres of economic activities in Nigeria, and one of the major cities of the Niger Delta, located in Rivers State. The local government area covers 260 km² and at the 2006 Census held a population of 464,789. Its postal code or ZIP code is 500102. Obio-Akpor has its headquarters at Rumuodomaya. The original indigenous occupants of the area are the Ikwerre People

Population of the Study

The population of the study is not known. Thus, it comprised of all betting youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, both males and female who engage in any form of football betting formed the targeted population of this study.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample size of 400 was adopted. To determine the sample size for the study, the convenience sampling technique was used. The reason is because since the population of football betting youths is not known in Obio Akpor LGA, the researcher used the numbers of respondents that could be easily accessed and reached. The convenience sampling technique again was used to select five communities given the availability of time and resources to represent the entire communities where betting are done. These zones are Elimgbu, Rumuolumeni, Choba, Rumuodumaya and

Rumuokoro. After this, purposive sampling technique was used to identify 4 betting centers in each zone, having 20 betting centres. Furthermore, the researcher allocated 80 samples to each zone and each betting unit had 20 samples using purposive sampling.

Types of Data and Instrument for Data Collection

The researcher utilized the integration of both primary and secondary data. The primary data involved the use of questionnaire. As for the secondary data, it adopted the use of published and unpublished material. As for the questionnaire instrument which is a form of primary data, a self-designed instrument titled Football Betting and Depression Questionnaire (FBDQ) were used as instruments for data collection. The instrument was segmented into two sections, such as A and B. The section A is known as Socio-demographic data, it was used for the collection of personal information from the respondents like location, gender, socio-economic background, age and class. Section B consisted of items that elicit responses from the respondents based on their feelings and opinions given the variables of the study. The section B of the instrument patterned alongside the Likert scale. All the items responded to a 4-points modified Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1, respectively.

Validity of the Instruments for Data Collection

The content validity was used. To achieve this, the researcher submitted the designed instrument to the supervisor and two other experts in Department of Sociology for content validity. The

experts will vet and make corrections were necessary. These corrections were incorporated in structuring the final draft of the instruments. The instrument therefore adjudged reliable to be used.

Reliability of the Instruments for Data Collection

To determine the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest technique was used. The researcher visited and administered the same instrument to a sample of 40 football betting youths in Ikwerre local government area, Rivers State which was outside the sample of the study at two weeks interval. The 40 respondents represent 10 percent of total sample size which is standard in research agendum (Wilson, 2020). A reliability coefficient above 0.80 was obtained as the data was subjected to Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher visited the sampled betting centres in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area that were used for the study and administered the 400 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents (football betting youths). The researcher also sought the services of research assistance for distribution of questionnaire and its retrieval. The essence of this was to ensure high percentage return. The researcher at each occasion explained the purpose of the study, the content of the questionnaire and mode of completion to the respondents.

Methods of Data Analysis

Various statistical tools were adopted to analyze the data. The charts, mean (\bar{x}) and independent T-test were used for analysis. The researcher used these tools in different ways. First,

the bio-data was used to analyze the socio-demographic characteristics. The mean (\bar{x}) was used as statistical tools to answer the research questions. Finally, the independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Research Question One: How do the trends of football betting affect the change in appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 1: Showing statistical scores for how the trends of football betting among football betting youths affect the change in appetite of youths who engage in this game

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Mean	Dec
1	I often engage in football betting	150	160	50	40	3.50	A
2	Correct Score is one of the games introduced	174	160	36	30	3.72	SA
3	Football betting has become more popular among youths in recent years	142	170	48	40	3.32	A
4	Do you accept that some betting youths plays double chance	140	175	65	20	3.52	SA
5	Do you agree most youths bet on Virtual football and Motorcycle Racing	192	150	45	13	3.51	SA

Source: Fieldwork, 2023.

The above table shows statistical score for how the trends of football betting among football betting youths affect the change in appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. First, item 1 on often engagement in football betting had the mean score of 3.50. Secondly, item 2 on correct score is one of the games introduced had a mean score of 3.72. Also, item 3 on football betting has become more popular among youths in recent years had a mean score of 3.32. Item 4 that that some betting youths plays double chance had a mean score of 3.52. Finally, item 5 on mean score of 3.5. With the homogeneity in the result, it implies that all the items support they are the trends of football betting youths that affect the change in appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Test of Hypothesis

H0: The more the youths involves themselves in football betting and also becomes unsuccessful in the game, the more they become depress in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

Table 1: T-Test analysis for youths football betting, becoming unsuccessful in the game, and becoming depress

Table with 8 columns: Variable, Mean, SD, Standard error, DF, Calculated T-value, Critical T-value, Remark. It contains two rows of data for different items related to football betting and depression.

Source: Research Fieldwork (2023).

Two items were selected to test the hypothesis. First item specified emotionally depressed whenever I lose a bet and the second was my family always see me as not responsible due to my habit of betting. The table shows that the calculated t-value is 7.453, while the critical t-value is 1.064 at 0.05 level of significant and at 398 degree of freedom. Since the calculated T-value is greater than the critical t-value at 0.05 level of significance, the result shows that the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This means that the more the youths involves themselves in football betting and also becomes unsuccessful in the game, the more they become depress in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Trends of Football Betting among Football Betting Youths

The study was able to find the trends of football betting among football betting youths in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. First of all, it was found that most youths often engage in football betting, and they usually play correct score which is one of the games introduced in football betting. Again, football betting has become more popular among youths in recent years and some betting youths play double chance as well as bet on Virtual football and Motorcycle Racing. All these trends and others are football betting that in one way or the other affected youths by making them depressed. Despite all this, study by Sen (2016) revealed that there are increasing Popularity of Football betting and this has experienced significant growth in popularity over the years. The ease of online betting platforms and the widespread availability of mobile apps have contributed to this trend. Also, he added that football is a globally popular sport, and as a result,

football betting has a wide international reach as major football events like the FIFA World Cup and UEFA Champions League attract a substantial amount of betting activity. Chuks (2019) who looked at trends in football betting presented that there has been a rise in in-play or live betting. This allows bettors to place wagers during a match, taking advantage of real-time events and changing odds. In-play betting offers an interactive and dynamic experience for football bettors. More importantly was the mobile betting; this technology has revolutionized the way people bet on football. With the availability of dedicated betting apps, users can easily place bets from their smartphones or tablets, making it convenient and accessible.

Summary of the Findings

The result showed the trends of football betting include correct score, more popular of betting, plays double chance, and **virtual football and motorcycle racing, thus**, that it has adverse effect that prompt change in appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Summary and Conclusion

The study investigated how the trends of football betting affect change in the appetite of youths who engage in this game in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The study carefully considered how the the fact that football betting is becoming a disturbing trend following the psychosocial issues arising from such activity in Obio-Akpor and other areas. Thus, the scope of the study was delimited into geographical scope which covers the study within Obio/Akpor Local Government Area Rivers State, while the unit of analysis will be selected football betting youths

in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State; and the content scope, addressing the issue football betting and depression. In the same line, the study operationalized some concepts vital concepts that relate to the study such as football betting, betting, depression, etc. Methodologically, the study adopted a correlation research design as it helps to employ the use of quantitative research approach (questionnaire) to get the view of the sample respondents. The sample size of 400 was used determined through convenience sampling technique. The research instrument used was questionnaire. The validity of the instrument was content validity, the help of my supervisor and two other experts were given a draft to effect corrections. The method of data analysis included the following: chart, mean and T-test. The study has been able to explain the issue of football betting and depression among youths. Depression is not a positive concept and that necessitated the study findings with the intent to give some justifiable recommendations. While some people engage in sports betting without any notable at-risk behaviours, for others it can become a dangerous addiction and trigger depressive symptoms. Left untreated, sports betting addiction can have many negative social, psychological and physical repercussions. These include relationship conflict and breakdown; debt, financial problems and bankruptcy; work issues and job loss; stress, anxiety and depression; and insomnia, lack of appetite and stomach problems. In extreme cases it can lead to suicidal thoughts and attempts.

Recommendations

It may not be easy for youths to completely avoid various aspect of betting as new ones keeps unfolding without considering its implications, there should be need for total abstinence. Secondly

in situation where it becomes difficult to abstain, the youths should conduct thorough research and analysis. This is because successful betting requires knowledge and understanding of the teams, players, and various factors that can influence match outcomes. Before placing a bet, invest time in researching team form, injury news, head-to-head records, home and away performances, and other relevant statistics. Relying on informed decisions based on accurate and up-to-date information can help you.

REFERENCES

- American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th Edn.* doi: 10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596
- Armstrong, A., & Carroll, M. (2017). Gambling activity in Australia—findings from wave 15 of the HILDA survey. *Australian Gambling Research Centre, Australian Institute of Family Studies.*
- Ayandele, O., Popoola, O., & Obosi, A. (2019). Influence of demographic and psychological factors on attitudes toward sport betting among young adults in Southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Gambling Studies, 35*(5) 343–354.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theories.* Prentice Hall.
- Browne, M., Langham, E., Rawat, V., Greer, N., Li, E., Rose, J., Rocklof, M., Donaldson, P., Thorne, H., Goodwin, B., Bryden, G., & Best, T. (2016). Assessing gambling-related harm in Victoria: A public health perspective. Victorian Responsible Gambling Foundation.

- Bunn, C., Ireland, R., Minton, J., Holman, D., Philpott, M., & Chambers, S. (2019). Shirt sponsorship by gambling companies in the English and Scottish Premier Leagues: Global reach and public health concerns. *Soccer and Society*, 20(6), 824–835.
- Burke, W. J. (2009). Fitting and interpreting Cragg's tobit alternative using Stata. *The Stata Journal*, 9(4), 584–592.
- Chikotora, P. (2016). *Motives for gambling in sports betting among Gweru residents*. A dissertation submitted to the Faculty of Social Sciences in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the BSC honours degree in Psychology Gweru, Zimbabwe, Midlands State University
- Cowlishaw, S., & Kessler, D. (2016). Problem gambling in the UK. Implications for health, psychosocial adjustment and healthcare utilisation. *European Addiction Research*, 22(10)90–98.
- Cragg, J. G. (1971). Some statistical models for limited dependent variables with application to the demand for durable goods. *Econometrica*, 39(5), 829–844.
- Deans, E. G., Thomas, S. L., Daube, M., & Derevensky, J. (2016). I can sit on the beach and punt through my mobile phone: The influence of physical and online environments on the gambling risk behaviours of young men. *Social Science and Medicine*, 166,(9) 110–119.
- Deans, E. G., Thomas, S. L., Daube, M., & Derevensky, J. (2017). The role of peer influences on the normalisation of sports wagering: A qualitative study of Australian men. *Addiction Research and Theory*, 25(2), 1–11.

- Deans, E. G., Thomas, S. L., Daube, M., Derevensky, J., & Gordon, R. (2016a). Creating symbolic cultures of consumption: An analysis of the content of sports wagering in advertisements in Australia. *BMC Public Health*, *16*, 208–215.
- Deans, E. G., Thomas, S. L., Derevensky, J., & Daube, M. (2017b). The influence of marketing on the sports betting attitudes and consumption behaviours of young men: Implications for harm reduction and prevention strategies. *Harm Reduction Journal*, *14*(1), 1–12.
- Deans, E.G., Thomas, S.L, Derevensky, J. & Daube, M. (2017). *The influence of marketing on the sports betting attitudes and consumption behaviours of young men: Implications for harm reduction and prevention strategies*. US National Library of Medicine National Institutes of Health.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Dowling, N. (2014). *The impact of gambling problems on families (AGRC Discussion Paper No. 1)*. Australian Gambling Research Centre, Melbourne.
- Dowling, N., Oldenhof, E., Cockman, S., Suomi, A., Merkouris, S., & Jackson, A. (2019). Problem gambling and family violence: Factors associated with family violence victimization and perpetration in treatment-seeking gamblers. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, *36*(15–16), 7654–7669.
- Eboh, V.C. (2015). *Prevalence and determinants of gambling behaviour among undergraduate students*. (A case study of Federal University OyeEkiti). A research project submitted to the Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities FOYE for the award of Bachelor of Science.
- Fulton, C. (2017). *Developments in the gambling area: Emerging trends and issues supporting the development of policy and legislation in Ireland*. Department of Justice and Equality
- Gainsbury, S. M. & Derevensky, J.L. (2013). Betting patterns for sports and races: a longitudinal analysis of online wagering in Australia. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, *11*(8), 1-16
- Gainsbury, S. M. & Derevensky, J.L. (2013). *What do we currently know about the impact of new media gambling games upon current and future gambling among young people?* Presented at the 15th International Conference on Gambling & Risk Taking, Las Vegas, Nevada

- Gainsbury, S. M., Hing, N., Delfabbro, P., Dewar, G., & King, D. (2014). An exploratory study of interrelationships between social casino gaming, gambling, and problem gambling. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 13(1), 136–153.
- Georgiu, D (2015). *Trends in Gambling Behaviour 2008-2014*. London.
- Greene, W. H. (2018). *Econometric analysis (8th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Haba, S. (2020). *What is the difference between betting and gambling?* <https://pediaa.com/what-is-the-difference-between-betting-and-gambling/>
- Hing, N., Lamont, M., Vitartas, P., & Fink, E. (2015). Sports-embedded gambling promotions: A study of exposure, sports betting intention and problem gambling amongst adults. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 13(1), 115–135.
- Hing, N., Russell, A. M., & Browne, M. (2017). Risk factors for gambling problems on online electronic gaming machines, race betting and sports betting. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 779. [11].
- Hing, N., Russell, A., Lamont, M., & Vitartas, P. (2017). Bet anywhere, anytime: An analysis of Internet sports bettors' responses to gambling promotions during sports broadcasts by problem gambling severity. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 33, 1051–1065.
- Hing, N., Russell, A., Thomas, A., & Jenkinson, R. (2019). Wagering advertisements and inducements: Exposure and perceived influence on betting behaviour. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 35, (9) 793–811.
- Hing, N., Russell, A., Vitartas, P., & Lamont, M. (2016). Demographic, behavioural and normative risk factors for gambling problems amongst sports bettors. *Journal of Gambling Studies*, 32(5) 625–641.
- Ogbanga, M. M. (2024). *Communication Skills in Social Work*. EduPedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Ogbanga, M. M. (2024). *Oil, Gender and Unemployment: Social Issues in the Niger*. Eduindex.
- Sharma, S. N. (Ed.). (2016). *New perspectives in sociology and allied fields*. EduPedia Publications (P) Ltd.

Uzochukwu, C. & Ohiri, K.E. (2021). An assessment of patterns, risks and effects of online sports betting among youths in South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 6(4), 172-179